

Executive Summary

Policy Brief

Restoring the Night: A Policy Agenda for Light Pollution Mitigation in Europe

Natural darkness and dark skies have long **shaped ecosystems and human civilisation**, guiding biological rhythms and inspiring culture, science, and a sense of cosmic connection. However, the **widespread** use of artificial light at night (**ALAN**), especially when used excessively or poorly managed, has disrupted these natural processes, making **light pollution one of the fastest-growing forms of environmental degradation**.

KEY MESSAGES

- Approximately **30% of vertebrates** and **over 60% of invertebrates** are **nocturnal**.
- **Light pollution** brings **significant environmental threats**, impacting biodiversity through disrupting vital processes and behaviours.
- While recognising the **beneficial** and important **role** of **ALAN** in providing human comfort, well-being and safety, its use must be **carefully balanced** to meet the needs of both **people and nature**.
- Globally, light pollution contributes to an estimated **3.4 trillion USD in lost ecosystem service value each year**.
- **ALAN causes light pollution** when humans, other organisms, or the environment are **exposed to unwanted or unnecessary lighting**. ALAN has to be **used and managed within** appropriate **ecological limits**.
- Like other forms of pollution, **light pollution should be integrated into the European environmental protection framework**, with continuous measurement and monitoring to strengthen nature conservation efforts.
- **ALAN has increased thousands of times** compared **to 200 years ago**, **with 99% of Europe's population** and biodiversity now living **under light-polluted skies**.
- To align with the international agenda and **recent regulatory developments**, the **EU needs to support action to reduce light pollution** and establish a coherent, harmonised framework for Member States.

Despite growing scientific evidence on the harmful impacts of ALAN, **light pollution remains largely overlooked in the EU's political agenda**. There is an urgent need to integrate it into the broader environmental protection framework. Recognising natural darkness as an essential component of the environment is vital to strengthening overall conservation efforts.

A **holistic approach to ALAN**, valuing **natural darkness** and **appropriate lighting**, is needed, placing nature at the heart of planning, as with other environmental stressors. Given recent international developments and growing commitments among Member States (MS), the **EU** should **harmonise regulatory efforts** by providing a **framework to address light pollution** at the EU and national levels, and **closing regulatory gaps**.

Unlike other forms of pollution, light pollution is relatively easy to resolve with straightforward mitigation measures, providing for adequate, necessary and purposeful ALAN within appropriate ecological limits.

KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Recognise light pollution as a form of environmental pollution

which **impacts the environment**, biodiversity and ecosystem services, and **explicitly include** it in the **environmental regulatory framework**.

2. Recognise night as an integral part of nature

needed for its healthy functioning.

3. Define ecological limits

and **maximum permissible parameters** for **ALAN**, ensuring its **purposeful** and conscious **application** balancing human and environmental needs.

4. Set ambitious targets to reduce light pollution

including them in the EU Biodiversity Strategy, Zero Pollution Action Plan, and **relevant policies** to promote the achievement of environmental goals.

5. Develop a coherent regulatory framework

align with **recent international and national regulatory developments**, **urging** Member States to implement measures to **reduce light pollution**.

6. Require light pollution monitoring and assessment

to **assess the magnitude, growth and impacts** of light pollution in the **EU**.

7. Ensure openness and transparency of data

concerning **ALAN sources** and light pollution levels, fostering a free exchange of information.

8. Support education and research

providing **support** for **education in lighting, lighting design** and **light pollution**.

9. Enhance and initiate awareness-raising campaigns

on light pollution and its impacts, and **advocate** for **interdisciplinary engagement**.

10. Promote international cooperation

and **coordinated action** to **address light pollution** as a transboundary environmental concern.

For further information, refer to [the Light Pollution Policy Brief](#). This policy brief is produced as part of the Horizon Europe [PLAN-B project](#) (Grant Agreement No. 101135308) in collaboration with its sister project [AquaPLAN](#) (Grant Agreement No. 101135471). It **provides strategic guidance** for the EU to **take steps** towards **addressing light pollution, recognising its adverse environmental impacts, harmonising efforts** and **providing a framework** for coordinated national action, as well as **promoting science-based regulation and management of ALAN**.

Recommended citation

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